

EXPERIENCES WITH INNOVATIVE LEARNING RESOURCES

Kotianová²² Janette, Červeňanská²³ Zuzana

Abstract

The article presents a survey and analysis of student feedback on learning materials designed to facilitate self-study. These materials were created with the aim of supporting student autonomy and improving the quality of education at technical universities. The study examines the effectiveness of these resources in terms of student engagement, student satisfaction, and perceived impact on their educational outcomes. In addition to student feedback, the article examines the experiences of educators. Special attention is paid to assessing changes in student behaviour, including their attitude to the learning process, class participation, and overall academic performance.

Keywords

innovative educational resources, education at technical universities, student feedback, experiences of educators, self-study

1 Introduction

Universities are constantly striving to increase student engagement and improve academic performance. Several researchers have introduced non-traditional teaching methods in the past two decades. However, there is no scientific consensus on the best innovative teaching methods adapted to students' abilities and at the same time most effectively address the course objectives (SAFAPOUR et al, 2019). To optimize student learning outcomes, several researchers and authors have introduced various innovative teaching methods and published them (BALALLE,2024), (BASRI, 2024), (HEILPORN et. al, 2021), (HIDAYAH et. al, 2024), (JAMSHIDOVNA & BAHODIROVICH, 2021), (JOHNSON et.al, 2016), (MAESAROH & SUTRISNO, 2025), (SAHNI, 2019), (SALEEM et. al, 2022), (SEPEHRI et. al, 2018), (SUBRAMANI & IYAPPAN, 2018), (ZUWALA & SZTEKLER, 2018).

Some of the innovative teaching methods currently used in universities include:

- Flipped Classroom: Students study lecture materials (videos, readings) at home and use class time for discussions, problem-solving, and hands-on activities.
- Blended Learning – A mix of online and face-to-face instruction that provides flexibility and personalized learning experiences.
- Problem-Based Learning (PBL) – Students work in groups to solve real-world problems, promoting critical thinking and teamwork
- Project-Based Learning: These are long-term projects in which students research, design, and present solutions, improving their creativity and practical skills.

²² Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Faculty of Materials Science and Technology in Trnava, Institute of Applied Informatics, Automation and Mechatronics, Jana Bottu 2781/25, 917 24 Trnava, Slovakia, janette.kotianova@stuba.sk.

²³ Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Faculty of Materials Science and Technology in Trnava, Institute of Applied Informatics, Automation and Mechatronics, Jana Bottu 2781/25, 917 24 Trnava, Slovakia, zuzana.cervenanska@stuba.sk.

- Gamification – Incorporating game elements (points, badges, leaderboards) to make learning more engaging and motivating.
- Virtual and Augmented Reality (VR/AR) – Immersive technologies that allow students to explore complex concepts interactively, such as medical simulations or virtual lab experiments.

2 Organization of our subject teaching

Our article describes experiences with innovative educational resources. At our faculty MTF STU we provide a course called Mathematical Methods of Experiment Planning and Evaluation (MMPVE). The content of this course is the basics of statistics and the basic principles of Design of Experiments (DOE). The group of students studying this course is large and diverse, ranging from 100 to 200. In the last academic year, 137 students were involved in this course. Approximately half of our students are studying in the normal mode in full-time study, half are studying in the combined method, and their schedule is concentrated in blocks. Class time allocation is 2 hours per week for lectures and 2 hours per week for seminars for on-site students. For combined-method students, the class allocation is 26 hours per semester for lectures and 26 hours per semester for seminars. In particular, these students who use the combined method are often of a higher average age and have been removed from school several years. They came to our faculty from different types of universities. Seminars in the subject are taught on computers. In the initial part of the course, students solve problems in combinatorics, probability, statistics, and regression analysis in Excel and then DOE experiments in Minitab software. Exercises with calculations on paper are not done at all in seminars. Calculations of solved statistics are done manually and supplemented with calculations on a computer only in lectures.

Given the above, we were motivated to look for solutions to increase the efficiency of studying this subject. Especially for students using the combined method, we wanted to make their difficult situation more manageable. Students were provided with a website with all available materials for their self-study, concentrated. They include lectures on individual topics, videos on selected thematic units, and Excel templates with tasks they solve with students. They also offer solutions to all tasks. Students have instructions on how to proceed with tasks in statistical analyses and the preparation of semester assignments, in which students design their experiment design, perform measurements, and evaluate it according to the instructions in the assignment. They have access to consultations with the teacher when solving problems that arise during their implementation and evaluation of the analysed data. The website also contains links to interesting websites, access to courses from other universities, animations, and other resources so that the student can supplement his knowledge and gain new experiences and ideas in teaching statistics, regression analysis, and DOE ideas. Before the final exam, they can self-test their knowledge on an e-test, which contains questions of the same type as those they can expect on the final exam for the subject. In this way, we tried to provide an opportunity for those students who need more time to study to self-study at home.

3 Final rules for subject assessment

The final evaluation of students in the MMPVE subject was based on the sum of the points they received during the semester from the continuous written test, the evaluation of the final complete semester work from their experiment, which they could do in a group with another person, and the final exam. During the final exam, students wrote an e-test, requiring a minimum success rate of 56%.

4 Our experiences

4.1 Student feedback on study materials and teaching methods

Students were asked to answer questions in an anonymous questionnaire at the end of the academic year after completing the course and passing their exam. A total of 38 students completed the questionnaire. Here are some selected questionnaire questions and recorded student responses.

Question 1. What is your overall assessment of the MMPVE subject?

Table 1 shows the absolute and relative numbers of responses received to this question. The pie chart in Figure 1 presents the distribution of students' responses to this question.

Tab. 4: Table of students' answers related to the overall assessment of the MMPVE subject

What is your overall assessment of the MMPVE subject?		
Students' answers	Count	%
Positive	28	74
Negative	6	16
Others	4	10
Total	38	100

Source: Own processing

Fig. 1: Chart of students' answers related to the overall assessment of the MMPVE subject

Source: Own processing

Answer other included students' answers:

- Neutral.
- It is a shame that we had something like this for the first time at a technical school (4th year of study).
- Positive thanks to the teacher, otherwise the subject is negative.

Question 2. What would you change about the content of MMPVE? What did you feel was missing in the subject, and what, on the other hand, seemed unnecessary?

We select some of the students' answers:

- The preparation of the semester assignment was too difficult for me.
- It would require more hours of statistics.
- I would add more on the topic of DOE.
- It isn't easy because there is much material.
- There was a lot of content, and we covered a new topic in every lesson.
- The subject content is okay. The teacher was also very friendly and willing to help. When solving the DOE, video lectures were available, which is a great addition. However, I missed more video lectures and content, which is not enough for a combined study. This would solve the problem.
- It is hard to say what I would change. Probably just my approach.
- I am very grateful for the content of the recording with the solution of the example from a continuous random variable, which was on the midterm test. The video was long, but it helped me a lot. It was a good feeling that I understood everything.
- I did not find anything unnecessary. I would have added more exam tests for practice.

Question 3. What would you change about the organization of the teaching process of MMPVE? What did you feel was missing in the lessons, and what seemed unnecessary?

We select some of the students' answers:

- I would remove the homework every week and insert it into the created submission point in the system.
- It might be a good idea to have more weekly exercises to cover all the content earlier. This would allow us to start working on the final semester project earlier.
- Go slower in the exercises.
- I could not do the assignments on the computer during the exercises; it was too fast.
- I see a problem with the combined method of study, with the lack of time for the lectures on the subject. I have not encountered a more complex topic.
- I would not change anything. The teachers are great, professional and empathetic.
- Lectures in electronic format (videos) are essential for students using the combined method.
- When working on the final semester assignment, allow working in a group of 2-3 people.
- Everyone should work on the semester assignment alone, not in a team.

Question 4. Did the sample exam test help you prepare for the exam?

Table 2 shows the absolute and relative numbers of responses received to this question. The pie chart in Figure 2 presents the distribution of students' responses to this question.

Tab. 2: Table of students' answers related to the question of the usefulness of the sample exam test

Did the sample exam test help you prepare for the exam?		
Students' answers	Count	%
Yes	35	95
No	0	0
Others	2	5
Total	37	100

Source: Own processing

Fig. 2: Chart of students' answers related to the question of the usefulness of the sample exam test

Source: Own processing

Answer other:

- No, because a person tries a test and does not know how to find the correct solution.
- It was beneficial to prepare the DOE assignment and spend two evenings studying and reviewing the lectures and materials. The test was a great help.

Question 5. Have you used the virtual catapult application?

Table 3 and the pie chart in Figure 3 present the students' responses to this question.

Tab. 3: Table of students' answers related to the question of using virtual catapult application

Have you used the virtual catapult application?		
Students' answers	Count	%
Yes	19	53
No	17	47
Total	36	100

Source: Own processing

Fig. 3: Chart of students' answers related to the question of using virtual catapult application

Source: Own processing

Question 6. I used the subject MMPVE

Table 4 shows the absolute and relative numbers of responses received to this question. The pie chart in Figure 4 presents the distribution of students' responses to this question.

Tab. 4: Table of students' answers related to the question of using the website during the semester

I used of the subject MMPVE		
Students' answers	Count	%
During the whole semester	24	63
Only during the exam period	14	37
Total	38	100

Source: Own processing

Fig. 4: Chart of students' answers related to the question of using the website during the semester

Source: Own processing

Question 7. What do you evaluate as positive on the MMPVE subject website?

We select some of the students' answers:

- The site is very clearly processed and categorized. I found everything I needed there, and the solved exercises were great. I have no negative comments about the site.
- Clarity, no unnecessary things.
- Everything is clearly in one place, including tests, worked-out solutions to tasks, and Excel templates.
- Everything is good. The site is helpful.
- All documents are in one place, including solved Excel exercises.
- I rate the overall access to information positively. It is an excellent addition for teachers.
- I rate the site positively because it contains all the necessary information and materials. There are no such advantages in another subject. I appreciate the videos, examples, and other materials that helped me complete the subject.

Question 8. What do you evaluate as harmful on the MMPVE subject website?

We received no responses that negatively evaluated the provided materials or the MMPVE subject website.

5 Discussion of student feedback

In this section we would like to discuss the survey results and summarize the feedback from the participating students. We acknowledge that our sample size (38 students) was insufficient. To ensure statistically reliable conclusions with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error, at least 101 students from the total population of 137 should have completed the questionnaire. Although our sample is small and our survey was focused more on qualitative student feedback, and therefore it is not possible to draw meaningful quantitative conclusions and generalizations about students' opinions on the provided study materials and teaching methods, apart from some of the graphs above, we believe that the suggestions and attitudes of these students can bring valuable perspectives for the implementation of innovative teaching methods for others as well.

Question 1, which concerned the overall evaluation of the MMPVE subject, received positive responses from 28 respondents, representing 74% of the 38 responses collected. Six students (16%) responded negatively. A potential bias in the responses regarding the evaluation of MMPVE could be the possibility that only students with a positive attitude toward the subject chose to participate in the survey. To minimize response bias, we distributed the questionnaire anonymously after the course had ended, ensuring that participation would not influence students' grades. We also recorded negative responses and appreciate that these students were willing to share their suggestions for improving the subject.

In Question 2, where we asked students what they would change about the content of the MMPVE course, we received highly diverse responses. Some students felt the content was too extensive, while others suggested adding more material. The students' answers to Question 3, which concerned the organization of the MMPVE teaching process, were equally diverse. However, most of the recorded answers focused on slowing down the pace of teaching in classes and providing more time for developing the semester project. Suggestions for increasing the time allocation or adjusting the lesson schedule are beyond our implementation capacity. However, by providing study materials that support self-study, students can independently manage the pace of their studies. It can be stated that the varying responses to Questions 2 and 3 were influenced by the students' **different personality types** and **individual learning styles**. While some students prefer **brief explanations**, others benefit from **detailed descriptions with contextual explanations**.

Question 4 asked students about a sample exam test that contained questions similar to the actual exam. The survey results indicate that students positively evaluated the availability of a sample exam test. In previous years, when no sample test was provided, students often requested one. However, some students now consider the test insufficient and expect the correct answers to be provided. They do not like to search for the correct answers in the study materials. Experience has shown that when students are given the correct answers directly, many memorize them without fully understanding the concepts. As a result, they are often surprised by incorrect results when changing the numerical values. Currently, we provide correct answers to questions on the subject page. In contrast, some questions in the academic information system remain without a correct answer – students only receive the final score for each question.

Question 5 asked whether students had used the virtual catapult application. The responses were nearly evenly split: 19 students (53%) used the provided simulation model, while 17 (47%) chose to design and implement their experiment. The virtual catapult was evaluated positively.

Question 6 asked whether students used the MMPVE subject website throughout the semester or only during the exam period. The answers were again divided approximately in half. Only 63% of respondents indicated using the website during the semester. The rest relied

on the provided materials only when preparing for the exam. Unfortunately, this reflects a common tendency among university students to engage with study materials only when forced to. On the other hand, students evaluated the provided website positively, and we did not record any negative responses to it (Question 7 and Question 8).

We wanted to verify whether the obtained quantitative data were correlated. Given the calculated values of 0.19, 0.15, and -0.05, it makes no sense to consider a correlation between the measured numerical responses.

6 Teachers' observations and experiences.

In this place, we select some of the observations of the teachers that they noted during the lessons:

- The offered solutions were beneficial for students studying using the combined method because studying in blocks is very difficult. On the contrary, the offered solutions to the assignments for full-time students were not a good choice. A specific group of students became passive, they stopped working actively in the classroom lessons.
- Although full-time students expressed dissatisfaction with the continuous submission of assignments during the semester, according to the observations of the teachers this was a good activity, because there were students in the group who, after the abolition of this obligation, stopped working actively on solving the tasks during the semester and only sat passively without interest in the exercises, or went to other websites for entertainment.
- When implementing the DOE experiment in school conditions and measuring the catapult range values, which the students subsequently statistically analysed, the joy and enthusiasm of the participating students were visible. Even though our primary goal is to teach students mathematical, or rather statistical thinking, this inclusion in the experiment was a strong motivating element.
- Although students stated that the final semester assignment is time-consuming, we believe that they learned the most while preparing for its assignment tasks. Students also shared this opinion with us during the final exam. We assume that the skills learned in this way will remain more permanent.
- As part of the survey of interest in MMPVE, a questionnaire was used to determine whether the student would like to continue in the given subject. Although most students stated that the subject was complex, out of 38 responding students, 20 expressed their opinions positively, and 18 expressed their opinions negatively.
- We positively assess that some students did not use the simulation applications we provided when obtaining experimental data. Instead, these students decided to make measurements in a unique laboratory in their department. We evaluate this significantly positively, especially considering that we educate technical engineers.
- We also see it as a positive aspect that, in recent years, students, especially doctoral students, have asked us if they can retake the MMPVE subject. By organizing teaching in this way, with all materials permanently available in one place and continuously updated with new facts and outputs generated from our research activities and studies, we believe that we are supporting their studies and careers in this way. This does not mean that they should no longer contact us. Of course, we teachers are pleased to see them in person, because it is also an opportunity for us to be at the centre of current research and we often learn new knowledge thanks to them.
- In addition, the students contribute to the content of the collected materials by providing new measurements from laboratory experiments obtained in company conditions. With

our help, students create teaching applications and simulation applications with the generation of data suitable for statistical processing. New ones are being created as part of the final bachelor's theses. We feel that new students recognize the value of the studied content, as we strive to incorporate the latest, most up-to-date information. Overall, it can be stated that students do not perceive the subject as useless, although they admit to having respect for it.

- "On the contrary, we regret to admit that we have not been able to convince many students to study continuously throughout the semester rather than just before the exam. Despite emphasizing that the content is connected and that further study requires understanding previous concepts, many wasted their time during the semester. However, this does not apply to combined-method students. Some students confirmed this by stating, "I finally understood it only during the exam..."

7 Final overall evaluation of the success of passing the exam in the subject MMPVE by grade

Histograms describing the success rate of the study in the monitored period of three years are in the following figures. The histogram of the distribution of grades of the final evaluation of the MMPVE subject for the described period of the academic year 2023/2024 is in Fig. 1. The period of the previous two academic years 2022/2023 and 2021/2022 is in Fig. 2. The statistical evaluation of the resulting evaluation of the MMPVE subject according to the overall evaluation by comparing individual periods is not correct, because the evaluation methodology was changed at the faculty. According to the new criteria, all enrolled students who failed the exam received an FX rating, regardless of whether they participated in the exams. In the previous period, these students did not receive FX grades. Despite the observed tendency to reduce mathematical skills in the current population, it can be stated that the average overall success rate of passing the MMPVE subject has not considerably changed.

Fig.5 Exam results in the described academic year 2023/24

Source: faculty's academic information system

Fig.6 Results of exams at previous academic years 2022/23 (left) and 2021/2022 (right)

Source: faculty's academic information system

8 Conclusion

In this contribution, we have attempted to summarize our experiences with including innovative methods in the teaching process, specifically in teaching statistics and the basics of experiment design. We present students' opinions expressed in an anonymous questionnaire and describe teachers' experiences.

Reactions to the answers regarding the content and the teaching method were diverse. Most students were overwhelmed by the amount of content. Nevertheless, some students, on the contrary, wanted to supplement the content. Here, we see the benefits of the materials and the method we provided them. Each student could choose how deeply they wanted to study the issue and could choose their own pace of study. Everyone appreciated the concentration of all materials in one place. Students preferred videos to text. Regarding the study allowance, the prevailing opinion of students was that the number of hours of the course was not enough. Students wanted more exercises, more practical tasks solved on computers with Minitab software. We teachers agree with their opinion. Unfortunately, the students had no foundation in probability, statistics, and regression analysis on which to build the DOE experiment. We did not want to teach them to click on statistical software blindly. We are pleased that almost half of the students stated in the questionnaire that they would like to continue the subject if they had the opportunity. We believe how the subject was organized and the "different approach" within the possibilities contributed to our students' attitude.

In the future, we would like to expand the MMPVE subject to include data processing in Python, which, for example, students of the Institute of Applied Informatics, Automation and Mechatronics are familiar with and which is today one of the most sought-after programming languages in practice.

9 Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the Slovak Cultural and Educational Grant Agency KEGA within the project No. 009STU-4/2023.

10 Resources

- BALALLE, H. (2024). Exploring student engagement in technology-based education about gamification, online/distance learning, and other factors: A systematic literature review. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open* 9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2024.100870>
- BASRI, H. (2024) The Effectiveness of Blended Learning, Digital Literacy Programs, and Teacher Training on Student Outcomes in 2024. *Global International Journal*, Vol. 2 (No. 5). <https://doi.org/10.59613/global.v2i8.249>
- HEILPORN, G.; LAKHAL, S.; BÉLISLE, M. (2021). An examination of teachers' strategies to foster student engagement in blended learning in higher education. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-021-00260-3>
- HIDAYAH, A. N.; ANDERSON, J.; & GARCÍA, M. A. (2024). Innovative Blended Learning Approaches to Enhance Student Engagement in University. *JTL: Journal of Teaching and Learning*, 1(1), 1–21. Retrieved from <https://journal.as-salafiyah.id/index.php/jtl/article/view/100>
- JAMSHIDOVNA, B. M.; & BAHODIROVICH, F. S. (2021). Innovative methods and techniques in the education system. *Master Journals. Current research journal of pedagogics* 2 (11): 147-151 [doi:https://doi.org/10.37547/pedagogics-crijp-02-11-28](https://doi.org/10.37547/pedagogics-crijp-02-11-28)
- JOHNSON, L.; ADAMS BECKER, S.; CUMMINS, M.; ESTRADA, V.; FREEMAN, A.; HALL, C. (2016). *NMC Horizon Report, Higher Education Edition*; The New Media Consortium: Austin, TX, USA, [[Google Scholar](#)]
- MAESAROH., & SUTRISNO, H. (2025). Effectiveness of Project-Based Learning Model in Improving Critical Thinking Skills and Chemical Self-Efficacy. *Journal of Innovation in Educational and Cultural Research*, 6(1), 61-68. <https://doi.org/10.46843/jiecr.v6i1.2041>
- SAFAPOUR, E.; KERMANSHACHI, S.; & TANEJA, P. A. (2019). Review of Nontraditional Teaching Methods: Flipped Classroom, Gamification, Case Study, Self-Learning, and Social Media. *Education Sciences*, 9(4), 273. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci9040273>
- SAHNI, J. (2019). Does Blended Learning Enhance Student Engagement? Evidence from Higher Education *Journal of e-Learning and Higher Education* 14 pages, DOI: 10.5171/2019.121518
- SALEEM, A.N., NOORI, N.M. & OZDAMLI, F. (2022). Gamification Applications in E-learning: A Literature Review. *Tech Know Learn* 27, 139–159 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10758-020-09487-x>
- SEPEHRI, M., VARGAS M., L. F., & ADEEB, S. (2018). Evaluation of Student Experiences in a Developed Blended Learning Course in Engineering. Proceedings of the Canadian Engineering Education Association (CEEA). <https://doi.org/10.24908/pceea.v0i0.12975>

- SUBRAMANI, P.C., & IYAPPAN, V. (2018). Innovative methods of Teaching and Learning. *Journal of Applied and Advanced Research* 3. <https://doi.org/10.21839/jaar.2018.v3iS1.161>
- ZUWALA, J.; & SZTEKLER, K. (2018). Implementation of case study method as an effective teaching tool in engineering education. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference*, Tenerife, Spain, 17–20; pp. 89–94. doi: [10.1109/EDUCON.2018.8363213](https://doi.org/10.1109/EDUCON.2018.8363213).